

ERNEST SETON THOMPSON : NATURE AND LITERATURE

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Eshonqulova Nasiba Husniddin qizi

Master student of Bukhara State University

Annotation: *Seton's animal stories, pictures, and paintings as socially created ideas of nature, as appropriated space produced and reproduced by dominant power structures, are the subject of this article. According to this article, there are interwoven linkages between Seton-literary Thompson's works and nature.*

Keywords: *Ernest Seton-Tompson, naturalist, Black Wolf, animal anatomy, animal stories.*

“Good men are now at work with better thoughts, and reverence for the masterpieces, the giants of creation’s world.”

– Ernest Thompson Seton, 1900

Seton-Thompson, born Ernest Evan Thompson, was an award-winning wildlife illustrator and naturalist, as well as a captivating storyteller and lecturer, a greatest author of animal stories, a Native American Sign language expert, and an early supporter of First Peoples' political, cultural, and spiritual rights. He was born in South Shields, Durham, England, on August 14, 1860, of Scottish parents (both sides of the family fought for The Old and New "Pretenders"). He was the eighth of ten brothers to grow up; a sister died when he was six years old.

Throughout his life, he called by numerous names and nicknames, including Ah-pas-to (Sign Talker), given by the Blackfoot Nation in 1916, Mahto Ska, given by Yanktonais Chief White Bear in 1927, and shunka sapa (Black Wolf), granted by the Lakota Nation. In Woodcraft, he was known as Black Wolf. Chief, ETS, Wolf Thompson, and Wolf Seton were some of the nicknames he was given.

Ernest Seton Thompson was engaged mostly in spatial practice of witnessing and codifying nature and the non-human world from the eighteen eighties until just before his death in 1946. His analysis reveals a persistent nexus in the political harness of the natural environment. Those effects are still present in the stories we tell ourselves about human beings in the modern world.

Seton created nearly 40 books, as well as thousands of illustrations, sketches, and paintings. He was a self - motivated person who was criticized as a misguided or outdated romanticist or, simultaneously, as an eco-radical, an artistic innovator, a social activist, and a man important to history. He was a tireless researcher, scientist, lecturer, traveler, and artist. During his lifetime, scientists and politicians such as John Burroughs, an American naturalist, and Theodore Roosevelt, an American President and forerunner of the Progressive Movement, both attacked and praised him (1900-1917). In terms of conservation, the effort transformed enormous swaths of wilderness

into parks, with the goal of "making the forest produce," as Roosevelt's advisor and Forest Service founder Gifford Pinochet put it. Seton's notions about woods and the species that lived in them, as well as man's involvement with the environment, were diametrically opposed to conservation.

Seton understood animal anatomy as a classically educated artist, which gave his paintings and illustrations their realistic impact. The modernist agenda finally undercut the values of his Woodcraft League boy's club in the United States and Canada, and he became best known in North America for his animal stories [3, 12]. Lord Baden-Powell, ironically, co-opted Seton's vision of a group that brought boys closer to nature through an idealized depiction of Plains Indian culture and woodcraft. Baden-Powell racialized and militarized Seton's Woodcraft League with Roosevelt's support, granted Seton the status of co-founder, and renamed the organization the Boy Scouts of America. Seton eventually gave up his status and cut ties with the hierarchical club. Seton faced a lot of professional contestations during his career, but as a gentle guy, he did little to contest them.

Seton is known in North America as a naturalist, but he is best known as the creator of an unique Canadian literary form. He infused his animal stories with a realistic edge utilizing his highly developed talents of observation as a naturalist and artist, and while they were not literary successes, they made him a wealthy man due to their enormous popular appeal. Seton was a master of nature's "realistic illusion," one of only a few artist-scientists (a remarkable inter-disciplinarity for the time) who could persuade us that the natural world was still within our grasp.

Seton was at the pinnacle of his career in 1923, when he published *Wild Animals I Have Known* (1926), a collection of his short stories. In an article titled *Real and Sham Natural History*, John Burroughs, the famed American natural history philosopher, reviewed Seton's collection of stories. Burroughs questioned Seton's scientific credibility and labeled him a "nature faker" in his piece, claiming that: "The line between fact and fiction is repeatedly crossed and... a deliberate attempt is made to induce the reader to cross too... Mr. Thompson Seton says in capital letters that his stories are true and it is this emphatic assertion that makes the judicious grieve" [4,7].

Seton and his work, it seems to me, are trapped in a form of this divide between where the scientist ends and the artist (writer and painter) begins. Seton's encounters with people in response to his paintings, animal stories, and work as a naturalist can be seen as a representation of this ideological struggle, which is beneficial to the book's literability. As a scientist, he saw and decoded the natural world as an absolute material reality that signified both substantiality and transparency in positivist terms.

All in all, he became a proponent of the "realistic illusion," engaged in a flicker between man in his garden and man in the wilderness, by writing and painting about nature in a way that conveyed realism based on scientific observation. In this liminal space, Seton's artwork and stories are an act of agency against the type of capitalist conservationism Roosevelt was endorsing – but by creating a site of contestation through his mastery of the "realistic illusion," Seton unwittingly aided those invested

in the illusion of nature's transparency in order to continue depleting the land of natural resources. What needs to be addressed is that, as Lefebvre points out, "The apparent translucency taken on by...political forces in decline (the state, nationalism [even the environmental movement]) is that they can enlist images having their source in the earth or in nature...The fact is that natural space will soon be lost to view...Nature is also becoming lost to thought. Nature is now merely the raw material out of which the productive forces of a variety of social systems have forged their particular spaces [2 , 21].

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